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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Abstract 1

Main Theme: Staffing for Prevention

Presenting Author: Agnieszka Mierzwa

All Authors: Agnieszka Mierzwa, Magdalena Syrkiewicz-Świtła

Title: Ensuring safe working conditions in diagnostic imaging facilities – the role and responsibilities of managers

Healthcare should ensure the safety of both patients and staff during medical procedures. Imaging diagnostics (ID) relies on advanced hardware technologies; therefore, a modern ID manager should implement risk prevention strategies, ensuring a safe and compliant working environment as well as a secure space for providing medical services. The study utilized two methods: a survey and in-depth interviews. The survey questionnaire was directed at medical staff, while the in-depth interviews were conducted with managers of ID departments. In both cases, purposive sampling was used. The survey covered four hospital departments and six outpatient imaging diagnostic centers, with a total of 300 medical staff surveyed. The most critical factors for the proper functioning of an ID facility, as indicated by respondents, were good work organization (71.7%), staff competence and engagement (55%), properly functioning medical equipment (45.3%), and safety during medical procedures (35.0%). A total of 74.3% of respondents believe that work organization significantly impacts the health safety of both patients and staff during medical procedures. Moreover, 61.7% stated that the manager plays a key role in ensuring safe working conditions, while 62.0% believe that a good ID facility manager should ensure safe working conditions. The key role of the ID facility manager in ensuring the safety of working conditions and medical procedures includes: maintaining highly specialized medical equipment, adhering to safety and hygiene standards in departments, following radiological protection principles, and participating in the continuous improvement of medical staff's knowledge and skills.

Abstract 2

Main Theme: Staffing for Prevention

Presenting Author: Tomasz Dec

All Authors: Tomasz Dec, Magdalena Syrkiewicz-Świtła

Title: Possibilities of using evaluation studies in the diagnosis of quality management practices in the State Emergency Medical Services (PRM) system

This article presents the topic of evaluation studies, which may be used in order to diagnose the quality management practice in the Polish system of State Emergency Medical Services (SEMS, or in Polish language: PRM). Evaluation studies have proved to be an effective tool for assessment of the results of public policies, which also covers those performed within the healthcare sector. The method of research applied in this article bases on the analysis of secondary data sources (scientific publications). The data for this article were derived from the well-known article databases (EBSCO, PubMed, Google Scholar). The obtained results of the study of available literature also present evaluation studies as a plausible method to study quality management practice in SEMS/PRM system in Poland. Evaluation studies are based on specific principles which regulate the conduct of study, however, its key strengths are flexibility, scalability and internal modifiability, so that various problems of quality management can be evaluated according to the current research needs. Furthermore, the use of evaluation studies in various organizational units within SEMS/PRM

system could enhance competence and skills in PRM teams. This article suggests that evaluation studies could deliver positive results for the SEMS/PRM system in Poland in two ways. First is that it could offer precise and accurate diagnosis for quality management within the system. The second assumption is that evaluation studies could base on a designed evaluation model and provide a comprehensive insight into quality management practice.

Abstract 3

Main Theme: Modern Technologies: AI, Big Data, EBM

Presenting Author: Jolanta Pelszyńska

All Authors: Jolanta Pelszyńska, Magdalena Syrkiewicz-Świtła

Title: Artificial intelligence in trichology - usage and prospects

This article is aimed at prospects of use of AI technologies by trichology service providers. So far, AI has had a proved record track of use in various branches of the economy, which includes the healthcare sector. The experience of a healthcare professional embraces not only the core elements of service, such as diagnostics, evaluation and therapy. The authors of this article have collected data in the form of research articles which describe IA applications in healthcare and trichology services. These articles provide a basis for the descriptive analysis on how AI could be applied in trichology services dividing the possible areas into: diagnostics, treatment supervision, customer contact and marketing automation. The results of research, despite of their qualitative nature, present that AI is a promising technology to be used in trichology service venues (offices/clinics), which is based on the evidence of use among healthcare professionals, particularly dermatologists, whose area of expertise is near to trichology services. More importantly, trichology services can benefit from AI by its supportive effect for diagnostics, image analysis, but also sending reminders to customers. On the side of back office processes, AI may send marketing information to the potential and actual customers, but also provide customer service. The article shows some obvious facts on why AI should be used in trichology service venues providing the perspective of positive outcomes for the interested service providers. There may also be some obstacles in AI used that should be considered, and the implementers should adapt to them accordingly (legal limitations, required human involvement).

Abstract 4

Main Theme: Modern Technologies: AI, Big Data, EBM

Presenting Author: Andrzej Staniszewski

All Authors: Jadwiga Staniszevska, Andrzej Staniszewski

Title: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS ROLE IN THE FIGHT AGAINST THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed and exacerbated the existing healthcare system deficiencies. On the other hand, however, it has given a strong stimulus for the digital transformation of the entire healthcare system. Emerging technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), and Internet of Things (IoT) have proven to be helpful to fight the COVID-19 pandemic. The purpose of this review is to explore the practical applications of AI in COVID-19, and its role in diagnosis, identification of high-risk cases, treatment planning, and limiting the spread of the pandemic. A literature review of publicly accessible information in scientific journals as well as news articles from April 2020 to February 2024 to identify the

examples of the use of digital technologies in COVID-19. AI is the ability of machines to exhibit human skills such as reasoning, learning, planning, and creativity - to achieve specific goals. The major applications of AI in COVID-19 disease are for early detection and diagnosis of the infection. AI can quickly analyze irregular symptoms and other 'red flags' and thus alarm the patients and the healthcare authorities. ML techniques are being used in analyzing radiology images. DL uses layers of connected artificial neurons inspired by biological neurons to mimic human decision-making processes. Training DL models generally requires very large training datasets (Big Data). The IoT collects sensor data from all manner of physical devices and makes them available on the Internet. AI can also build an intelligent platform for automatic monitoring and prediction of the spread of SARS-CoV-2 virus. AI techniques have had a direct impact on supporting the process of diagnosis, estimation of epidemic trends, prognosis, and treatment of COVID-19 disease. AI has also been used for the development of effective and safe drugs and vaccines, and the reduction of workload of healthcare workers. Therefore, it has the potential to enhance the entire healthcare system efficiency during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Abstract 5

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Agnieszka Dyzmann-Sroka

All Authors: Agnieszka Dyzmann-Sroka

Title: Barriers and benefits of breast cancer prevention programs in Poland

Breast cancer is the leading kind of malignancy among women in Poland. Mammography is recognised as a non-invasive diagnostic technique; yet, there exists a notable deficiency in the frequency of routine preventative screenings among Polish women. The original questionnaire survey was designed under the direction of the article's author and conducted by students of Poznan University of Medical Sciences between June and August 2022. It involved 531 women aged 50-69 years. The study group was determined by women living in cities (63%) and currently working (72%) with higher and secondary education (38% each). Only 48% of the respondents have performed a mammography test in the last 2 years. The most commonly barriers were: fear 83% (of diagnosis, pain, unknown test, radiation, belief that mammography will cause cancer), indicate a lack of knowledge 43% (of where such a test can be done and about the test itself, that such a test can be done at all), 40% indicate a lack of time. The early detection of breast cancer significantly enhances the likelihood of achieving a full remission. Although most Polish women are aware that they can take a preventive test, still too few women take a mammogram. There is a need for modifications to be made in the precautionary screening system in order to enhance women's motivation to engage in preventive care.

Abstract 6

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Angelina Kaleta-Pilarska

All Authors: Angelina Kaleta-Pilarska

Title: The importance of Type D personality for mental adaptation to cancer in patients with colorectal cancer

Cancer diagnosis is a source of long-term stress for the patient. The patient's mental attitude to the disease directly affects the quality of their life and may also determine the effectiveness of the final therapeutic effects.

Determining the significance of Type D Personality for mental adaptation to cancer may have not only cognitive value. The study involved 200 patients diagnosed with colon cancer. The study used the Author's Personal Questionnaire, the Mini-MAC questionnaire, and the DS-14. The majority of the respondents (56.4%) with Type D Personality present a Destructive Style of Mental Adaptation to Cancer Disease. The significance of Type D Personality is evident after taking into account the presence of other cancer diseases, the patient's fitness level and alcohol consumption before the cancer diagnosis in the case of the Destructive Style of Mental Adaptation to Cancer Disease dominating the picture.

Abstract 7

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Dagmara Gawel-Dąbrowska

All Authors: Dagmara Gawel-Dąbrowska, Tomasz Zatoński, Katarzyna Zatońska, Marta Zając-Ossowska

Title: Zoo Wrocław strategic partner for health empowerment of seniors

The Wrocław Zoo as a place for family, social gatherings is part of the history of almost every Wrocław family. Nowadays, however, zoos are not only places of entertainment, but also organisations actively involved in conservation and health research. For many years, public health has been facing serious problems related to the ageing population and their quality of life. The aim of our project is to investigate the impact of zoo visits on the assessment of health and quality of life by visiting seniors, and to highlight the role of the zoo in undertaking activities of health-promoting importance. In the project, we observed a group of 214 people aged 60+, who visited the Wrocław Zoo once a quarter on three occasions. The controlled visit consisted of walking 6,000 steps. Before and after the visit, they completed the WHO QOL-26 questionnaire and Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ-short). The participants in the study were a group of 214 seniors (women 186 - 81%, men 43 - 19%) aged between 61 and 92 years, of whom nearly 70% were aged 65 to 74 years. The WHO QOL-26 questionnaire allows the assessment of quality of life in 4 domains: somatic, psychological, social and environmental. Analysis of the project's results indicated an increase in the quality of life of seniors - participants in the study - in all domains. In the study of physical activity, assessed by the IPAQ-short questionnaire, an increase in moderate and vigorous activity (according to the WHO guidelines for seniors) was also observed. Visits to the zoo can be an attractive way of activating senior citizens in the form of educational and health trails.

Abstract 8

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Nicholas Karolak

All Authors: Nicholas Karolak

Title: "Gym as a Place for Promoting a Healthy Lifestyle – How Fitness Clubs Can Become Centers of Health Prevention?"

Fitness clubs increasingly support healthy lifestyles, aiding in preventing diseases like obesity, cardiovascular issues, musculoskeletal disorders, mental health challenges, chronic respiratory diseases, and autoimmune conditions. Tailored exercises, guided by trainers or physiotherapists in consultation with doctors, are crucial. However, their potential as public health hubs in Poland remains underutilized. A literature review analyzed

the role of fitness clubs in health promotion and personal trainers' involvement in education. Key aspects included club offerings (workshops, consultations), trainers' roles (competencies and integration into public health systems), and client opinions (survey results). Findings highlighted current knowledge and identified gaps in integrating fitness clubs with public health initiatives. The review indicates that fitness clubs in Poland focus primarily on physical training, with additional services like dietary workshops, health consultations, and relaxation sessions rarely available. Personal trainers play a significant role in promoting healthy lifestyles, but their educational efforts are limited by a lack of training and public health knowledge. In countries where trainers are integrated into public health systems, preventive efforts are more effective. While clients view fitness clubs positively as health-supporting spaces, they note the lack of comprehensive educational programs. There is a strong demand for more dietary consultations and psychological support. Fitness clubs in Poland have untapped potential as public health promotion centers. Combining physical activity with health education, dietetics, and psychological support could enhance their role in preventing diseases like obesity and cardiovascular conditions.

Abstract 9

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Marta Jarosz

All Authors: Marta Jarosz, Julia Głuszek

Title: Supplementation or diet? - When are supplements necessary and when can diet be an alternative during cancer treatment?

The aim of this study is to evaluate the role of diet and supplements in cancer treatment and to determine when supplementation is necessary and when diet may be an alternative. Analysis of studies from PubMed indicates that supplementation with zinc, selenium and copper supports the immune response and cellular processes, which improves treatment efficacy. Analysis based on studies from the PubMed database on the effect of diet and supplementation on cancer therapy. Papers on zinc, selenium, copper, vitamin D3 and branched-chain amino acids were selected. The methodology involved searching the literature for the effectiveness of supplements, their interaction with chemotherapy and their impact on survival and quality of life of patients. Studies have shown that supplementation with zinc, selenium and copper supports the immune response and cellular processes, which improves treatment efficacy. A diet rich in fibre, fruit and vegetables with branched chain amino acids increases survival in HCC, reducing the risk of encephalopathy. Certain supplements, such as vitamins A, C, E and iron, may increase the risk of relapse. Vitamin D3 reduced mortality by 12%. Supporting cancer therapy requires a personalised approach, combining an antioxidant-rich diet with appropriate supplementation. Zinc, selenium and vitamin D3 improve treatment efficacy and survival. Supplements that may increase the risk of recurrence should be avoided. Patient education is key to understanding the benefits and risks of supplementation in cancer therapy.

Abstract 10

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Natalia Gąsiorowska

All Authors: Natalia Gąsiorowska, Justyna Niżyńska, Natalia Szarwaryn

Title: "Taking care of sleep hygiene as a public health challenge".

Sleep plays a key role in maintaining physical and mental health, providing the foundation for daily functioning and quality of life. Proper sleep hygiene habits have a significant impact on the body's ability to recover, concentration, emotional balance and performance in work and study. However, modern difficulties such as stress, excess digital stimuli and improper organization of time lead to widespread sleep disorders. The research for the study warranted a review and analysis of the literature related to the topic at hand, based on keywords-i.e. (sleep, hygiene, sleep disorders, insomnia, environmental factors, sleep length)- contained in the Google Scholar search engine database and scientific databases such as Pubmed between 2012 and 2017. The level of sleep hygiene depends on physical activity, the time of going to bed, access to TV and Internet in the bedroom, and the meals, drinks consumed before going to sleep. The causes of sleeplessness can be stimulants such as alcohol, caffeine and medications. Shift work and poor health can also lead to insomnia. Both too little sleep and overly prolonged sleep can carry serious consequences. Maintaining proper sleep duration (7-8 hours per night) is also important for the effectiveness of treating disorders and the coexisting obesity. Increased sleep duration can result in lower blood pressure in hypertensive patients. The daily functioning of society is determined by the maintenance of adequate sleep hygiene which ultimately translates into productivity, concentration, efficiency and quality of health. Maintaining proper sleep duration (7-8 hours) serves to improve recovery, cognitive function and overall physical and mental health, while reducing the risk of developing chronic diseases.

Abstract 11

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Aleksandra Sołtysiak

All Authors: Miłosz Lipieta, Aleksandra Sołtysiak, Dorota Kiedik, Tomasz Zatoński, Katarzyna Zatońska

Title: University community in health promotion program on the example of the project "Build Health with UMW"

Supporting healthy behaviors within university communities is essential for enhancing the quality of life and productivity of both students and staff. The "Build Health with UMW" project, carried out at Wrocław Medical University during the 2022/2023 academic year, aimed to analyze health-related behaviors and implement actions to promote a healthier lifestyle among participants. The program featured educational seminars, physical activity sessions, and social media campaigns, along with anthropometric and laboratory assessments for individuals at risk of metabolic disorders. In addition, a survey was carried out among employees to assess their needs related to health promotion and support for adopting a healthier lifestyle. The findings revealed notable challenges, including a high incidence of overweight and obesity, along with associated risks like insulin resistance and lipid imbalances. Participants showed a strong interest in health initiatives, with 90% of employees surveyed expressing the view that such programs should be supported by employers. Educational sessions and physical activities proved especially effective in increasing health awareness and encouraging behavior change. This article presents the results of the pilot program, highlights the identified health risks, and examines employee needs and expectations concerning health promotion in the workplace. The conclusions emphasize the need for comprehensive and long-term health initiatives that are specifically designed to meet the distinct requirements of academic communities.

Abstract 12

Main Theme: Lifestyle

Presenting Author: Aleksandra Sołtysiak

All Authors: Marta Grelowska, Aleksandra Sołtysiak, Dorota Kiedik

Title: Nicotine addiction in pregnancy – women's behavior and their knowledge about the harmful effects of smoking – a systematic review

Exposure of unborn children to maternal smoking or secondhand smoke is associated with birth defects, stillbirths, preterm births, and infant deaths. Maternal smoking during pregnancy is associated with a doubling of the risk of sudden infant death and birth defects, while exposure to secondhand smoke during pregnancy is associated with a 23% increased risk of stillbirth. The aim of the study is to determine whether knowledge about the harmfulness of nicotine addiction and awareness of its effects correlate with health-promoting behaviours of pregnant women. Inclusion criteria: studies conducted among pregnant women, studies on tobacco and e-cigarette use Exclusion criteria: studies conducted among women during the postpartum period or before conception; studies on stimulants other than tobacco, passive smoking Limitation of the study: only few studies conducted in Western and Central European countries, studies conducted mainly in patriarchal societies Results: Women know about the harmful effects of smoking during pregnancy, but they do not know the tools to do it properly and effectively. The lack of education about safe smoking cessation causes the abuse of e-cigarettes instead of traditional tobacco. Pregnant women often quit smoking during pregnancy for socio-cultural reasons. Pregnancy is a motivating factor to quit smoking. The topic of educating men on how to prevent passive smoking in pregnant women is gaining popularity. Conclusions: A thorough study should be conducted among Polish women/residents of Central Europe. There is a need to educate pregnant patients about the harmfulness of both e-cigarettes and traditional tobacco. A systematic program of educating pregnant women about ways to cope with quitting smoking should be introduced.

Abstract 13

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Magdalena Wrzesińska

All Authors: Magdalena Wrzesińska, Magdalena Wiczorkowska, Jarosław Rakoczy, Katarzyna Binder-Olibrowska

Title: Shift2Health Project: Development and evaluation of nutritional strategies to reduce and prevent obesity in shift workers.

Shift workers are at risk of obesity and metabolic health problems, but there is still insufficient knowledge of the determinants and a lack of evidence-based interventions in this area. The aim of this study is to map the biopsychosocial functioning of shift workers in the healthcare and industrial sectors. This international project is funded by the European Union and carried out from 2023 to 2028. An online questionnaire is used to explore the health issues of different sectors workers. Individual interviews with managers and focus groups with shift workers aim to understand their opinions and expectations regarding health and well-being. At this stage, it appears that shift workers suffer from sleep disorders, poor eating habits, lack of physical activity and increased stress levels. Employers' responses to the health of shift workers appear to be inadequate, as perceived by both workers and their managers, due to a number of individual, organisational and systemic barriers. These factors can be taken into account when developing interventions. Shift work can significantly affect biopsychosocial functioning and increase health risk. The Shift2Health project can provide important evidence for public health, workers and employers to reduce the risk of obesity in the affected population.

Abstract 14

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Magdalena Kostyła

All Authors: Magdalena Kostyła, Magdalena Wieczorkowska, Magdalena Wrzesińska

Title: Primary Cancer Prevention for Individuals with Mental Health Problems: Steps to Implement the Patient Navigation Model in Poland through Co-Design and Participation

Patient Navigation (PN) has been well demonstrated as a potential application in the continuum of cancer care in vulnerable populations, but further research is needed to identify barriers and opportunities that may affect the implementation of PN primary cancer prevention programs for people with mental health problems. The study used a qualitative approach to tailor a navigation-based intervention in primary cancer prevention to the needs of the target population and the local context. Semi-structured interviews (with 20 participants) and 3 focus group sessions (with 12 participants) were conducted with representatives of 5 stakeholder groups. Three primary themes emerged from the interviews for analysis: barriers to accessing healthcare services, facilitators of access, and considerations for the Patient Navigation Model (PNM). Based on the key considerations for designing patient navigation presented by DeGroff et al (2014), discussions during the focus group sessions centred around 10 issues: (1) program goals, (2) community characteristics, (3) point(s) of intervention, (4) setting(s) of intervention (5) the range of services and navigator's responsibilities, (6) background and competencies of the navigator, (7) communication channels, (8) navigator's training, (9) navigator's supervision, and (10) evaluation measures. Involving key stakeholders in implementation research offers the opportunity to develop an intervention tailored not only to the complex needs of recipients but also to the local context and real-life settings.

Abstract 15

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Magdalena Konieczny

All Authors: Magdalena Konieczny, Izabela Gąska

Title: Women participation in selected cancer prevention programmes

Breast cancer and cervical cancer prevention is an area in which there is still too little involvement of Polish women in free preventive examinations (mammography and cytology). Compared to other European countries, the participation rates of Polish women in prevention programmes are lower. Increasing women's participation in cervical cancer prevention and mammography is crucial for improving public health and early detection of cancer. A total of 415 women were included in the study. Women's participation in free prevention programmes for cervical cancer (cytology, 415 women) and breast cancer (mammography, 235 women) was analysed. A diagnostic survey method was used and the research tool was a Questionnaire Survey of our own design. Statistical calculations were performed using STATISTICA v. 13 ($p < 0.05$). 54.5% of women did not regularly participate in available cancer prevention programmes including 25.4% of those surveyed who had never had one. Women who had never taken part in this type of test did not do so for the following reasons: fear of being detected (65.3%), belief that they were healthy (45.3%), feeling uncomfortable during the test (44.5%), belief that this type of test is ineffective (15.5%), problems finding a facility where the test can be performed (11.2%). Women's participation in preventive oncology screening was unsatisfactory. Younger women, those with higher education and those living in urban areas, were more likely to participate in this type of tests compared to older women, those with lower education levels and those living in rural areas. Educational promotional and motivational activities should continue to be undertaken to increase women's awareness of the effectiveness of cervical and breast cancer prevention.

Abstract 16

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Joanna Kobza

All Authors: Joanna Kobza, Mariusz Geremek, Mateusz Grajek, Lechosław Dul

Title: The influence of NO_x, temperature, wind and total radiation on the level of ozone concentration in the Upper Silesian agglomeration

Air pollution is one of the leading threats to human life, therefore it is indicated as one of the main public health concerns. Recent studies have confirmed that the high number of annual excess deaths are associated with high levels of ozone, i.e. in 2019 ozone accounted globally for about 365 000 early deaths (6.21 million years of healthy life lost) The aim of the study was to estimate the influence of NO, NO₂, wind direction (WD) wind speed (WS), air temperature (TA), and total radiation (GLR) on ozone concentration levels. Data provided by 3 automatic air quality monitoring stations of the Regional Environmental Protection Inspectorate in Katowice, were used in this study. The study showed that the strongest influencing factors for O₃ values are air temperature and total radiation, with each showing a high correlation with ozone concentration. NO and NO₂ had a dual effect on O₃ concentration, causing an increase in ozone concentration at low NO and NO₂

concentrations and a decrease in ozone concentration at higher NO and NO₂ concentrations. We noted that the direction of the wind had very little effect on the concentration of O₃. The influence of wind speed on the O₃ level was also small, but stronger than that of the wind direction. The research shows that in the analysed years for selected measuring stations the strongest factors influencing O₃ concentration are air temperature and total radiation., the NO and NO₂ concentrations had a dualistic effect on the O₃ concentration.

Abstract 17

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Gabriela Krężel

All Authors: Gabriela Krężel, Magdalena Sikorska, Rafał Halik, Marcin Grysztar, Szczepan Jakubowski, Olena Stropalova, Mariusz Duplaga on behalf of the EUVABECO Consortium

Title: Review of practices supporting COVID-19 vaccinations during the pandemic in Poland and Ukraine

Vaccination is an efficient method of preventing infection transmission in society. The COVID-19 pandemic acted as a catalyst for implementing various strategies to enhance vaccination uptake. Identifying these actions was one of the first tasks planned within the EUVABECO project, co-funded by the European Union under EU4Health Grant N° 101132545. A scoping review, conducted to analyze vaccination practices that supported COVID-19 vaccination, covered the period from March 2020 to June 2023. The analysis drew from diverse sources, including scientific publications, recommendations, government documents, and media reports. The review identified 11 vaccination practices: 9 in Poland and 2 in Ukraine. These practices fell into three main categories: interventions to increase the healthcare system's capacity, actions to raise public awareness of vaccination, and activities to boost community engagement. The first category included expanding the pool of vaccinators (e.g., for pharmacists), improving access through mobile vaccination units, and prioritizing vulnerable groups for vaccination. The second category covered health education campaigns, counter-disinformation efforts, and actions to build public trust in vaccination. The third category focused on community engagement and mobilization, such as the "Growing Immunity" competition for municipalities in Poland. Various innovative approaches were implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic to increase vaccination uptake in Poland and Ukraine. These practices generally required a collaborative approach involving multiple stakeholders and professional groups. Evidence on the effectiveness of specific strategies remains limited however, as outcome evaluations of these practices were rarely conducted.

Abstract 18

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Iwona Janiak-Rejno

All Authors: Ewa Popowicz, Iwona Janiak-Rejno, Agnieszka Żarczyńska-Dobiesz, Jolanta Grzebieluch

Title: Pink October – Take Care of Yourself

In 2023–2024, Wrocław University of Economics and Business launched the 'Pink October – Take Care of Yourself' initiative to promote physical and mental health awareness, focusing on cancer prevention. Aimed at both women and men, the program highlighted cancer screenings and mental health support, expanding its scope to assist young adults facing psychological crises. To achieve its health awareness goals, 'Pink October – Take Care of Yourself' included expert-led lectures, interactive workshops on cancer prevention, and one-on-one sessions with psychologists for mental health support. Collaborations with top regional institutions, such as the Silesian Center for Oncology, Pulmonology, and Hematology, enhanced reach and credibility, providing participants with vital medical resources and expertise. The 'Pink October – Take Care of Yourself' event saw high engagement, with over 500 participants attending lectures, workshops, and consultations. Feedback indicated increased awareness and a positive shift in attitudes toward regular health screenings and mental well-being. Participants reported a more robust understanding of preventive health measures and felt more equipped to recognize mental health warning signs. Collaborations with regional medical institutions provided attendees practical resources, enhancing their access to further support. The initiative strengthened the university's role as a proactive health advocate, successfully integrating physical and mental health education within its community. The 'Pink October – Take Care of Yourself' initiative raised cancer prevention and mental health awareness through education, workshops, and individualized support. Collaboration with regional healthcare institutions improved access to resources, fostering an inclusive, health-focused culture at the university. This impactful program underscores the university's commitment to proactive health and mental wellness for students and faculty.

Abstract 19

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Barbara Grabowska

All Authors: Maja Łazarska, Luba Ślósarz

Title: Alcohol consumption among students of the Wrocław Medical University

Alcohol is one of the most popular stimulants available on the market. Poland has a huge problem with the amount of alcohol consumed. In addition, academic life may be a substrate reinforcing the habit of alcohol consumption. Purpose of the study is to investigate alcohol consumption among students of the Wrocław Medical University. The study involved 322 students of the Wrocław Medical University. The study used: a self-administered questionnaire with a metric and the standardized AUDIT Test. Most students, as many as 91%, currently consume alcohol. Most of the students surveyed admitted that they started drinking alcohol between the ages of 15 and 17. Wine and beer are the most frequently consumed alcohols by students of the Medical University of Wrocław. Most students reach for alcohol at meetings/events with friends. As many as 87% of the respondents admitted that alcohol is consumed in the family home. Most students declared that they do not intend to ever give up drinking alcohol. An AUDIT score suggesting low-risk drinking was obtained by 67% of the students surveyed. Alcohol consumption among students at the Wrocław Medical University is at low risk. Women have a lower level of alcohol problem compared to men. Place of origin does not

differentiate the level of alcohol problem among the surveyed students. Age of onset of alcohol consumption differentiates the level of alcohol problem.

Abstract 20

Main Theme: Varia (Other)

Presenting Author: Joanna Kobza

All Authors: Kamila Jaroń, Joanna Kobza, Paweł Juraszek, Mateusz Grajek

Title: Determinants of Doctor–Patient Communication in Terms of Patient Rights During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Today, the public does not want to be just a passive consumer of health services. Patients often expect to be informed and involved in decisions about their health. With better doctor–patient communication, patients are more likely to follow treatment recommendations. The study was conducted using a face-to-face survey method on a group of 203 adult, independent patients from 2021 to 2022 at a medical facility, i.e., a rehabilitation clinic. The purpose of this study was to assess the determinants of doctor patient communication in terms of patient rights. Patients who were active in communication (33%) wanted to ask questions or had the opportunity to ask the doctor questions, and thus, they were able to take an active part in the discussion with the doctor. In contrast, patients who were passive in communication (67%) did not want to ask questions or did not have the opportunity to ask the doctor questions. The authors' survey shows that respondents with active communication were significantly more likely than patients with passive communication (almost 100% vs. 86%) to obtain information about their condition ($p = 0.002$). Hence, the primary key element of the medical consultation is the appropriate amount and content of information given to the patient, providing explanations and answering questions. Also importantly, according to the results, active communication between patients and doctors was significantly influenced by female gender, higher education, and a positive evaluation of communication with doctors.

Abstract 21

Main Theme: Staffing for Prevention

Presenting Author: Nicholas Karolak

All Authors: Nicholas Karolak

Title: New Competencies of Personal Trainers in Poland – Integrating Knowledge of Public Health and Physical Activity.

Modern health challenges, including rising rates of obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases, highlight the crucial role of physical activity in prevention. Personal trainers can play a key role in promoting healthy lifestyles, but expanding their competencies in public health and first aid is essential. This study examines their educational needs. This review-based study analyzes scientific literature on personal trainers' roles in health promotion and their potential as leaders in preventive healthcare. It examines studies on trainers'

competencies, educational involvement, and training programs in Poland and globally. Industry reports highlighting increasing expectations for trainers in public health and collaboration with healthcare systems are also included. The literature review indicates that personal trainers in Poland recognize the need to enhance their competencies in public health and first aid. However, unified training programs combining theory with practice to support their role in preventing lifestyle diseases are lacking. Examples from other countries show that trainers can effectively promote health if their education includes basics of dietetics, health psychology, and collaboration with medical professionals. The review also highlights significant research gaps regarding trainers' roles in Poland's public health system, emphasizing the need for further studies and the development of comprehensive training programs. The analysis highlights the need to enhance Polish personal trainers' competencies in public health, first aid, and collaboration with healthcare systems. Trainers hold significant potential in promoting healthy lifestyles and preventing diseases like obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular conditions. Standardized training programs combining theory and practice are essential, alongside fostering collaboration with medical professionals to improve preventive care effectiveness in Poland.

Abstract 22

Main Theme: Staffing for Prevention

Presenting Author: Tetiana Gruzieva

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Title: MODERN DIRECTIONS OF IMPROVEMENT OF PERSONNEL TRAINING FOR THE PUBLIC HEALTH SYSTEM

Given the relevance of training a new generation of public health professionals, their equipping with modern knowledge and skills to implement the main operational functions of public health and form the necessary competencies, special attention should be paid to the content of educational programmes, their constant updating and consideration of stakeholders' interests. The study employed bibliosemantic, informational-analytical, medical-statistical, sociological methods, and content analysis methods. The research programme included the analysis of scientific literature, WHO and ASPHER documents, sociological surveys of stakeholders, students of the Master's programme in Public Health, and employers on the areas of improvement of the educational process. It was found that $98 \pm 2,1$ out of 100 students surveyed are satisfied with their curriculum, in particular its content, with the possibility of forming an individual learning trajectory, passing practice, participating in research and improving the program. Employers highly appreciated the practical orientation of training (95 ± 4.4 per 100 respondents), the quality of personnel, teaching-methodical, and logistic support, with the involvement of practitioners and representatives of employers. The majority of respondents consider the strategic directions of improving learning to be constant quality improvement, student-centered learning, practical orientation, internationalization of education, participation in scientific research. Studying the opinions of students, employers on the content and implementation of the Master of Public Health educational program allows for a comprehensive assessment of the learning process, identifying strengths, advantages, existing and potential problems. The results of the stakeholder surveys are the basis for a critical review of the educational program and its improvement in accordance with current needs.

